

EMPOWEREDbyNEIA

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Ecosystems Mapping and Planning through Open dialogue for Wider cooperation across EU Regions based on the Entrepreneurial Discovery

D2.1 – EDR Reports

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Executive Summary

The EMPOWEREDbyNEIA project conducted two **Entrepreneurial Discovery (ED) Workshops** aimed at fostering cross-regional collaboration and addressing challenges within the **Cleantech innovation** ecosystems across seven European regions. Both workshops involved representatives from all QH categories, ensuring diverse perspectives and fostering collaboration across regions. The total number of **Quadruple Helix stakeholders** attending was **62**, with the highest attendance from **industry (29)**, followed by **academia (17)**, **government (11)**, and **civil society (5)**. The main findings of each workshop are as follows:

ED Workshop PART I: Foundation for collaboration

- **Identified challenges and opportunities** across regional innovation ecosystems.
- Highlighted **nine critical areas for collaboration**, including addressing skills gaps, improving public procurement regulations, and supporting startups with financial instruments.
- Key outputs emphasized the **need for stronger interregional partnerships** and **actionable strategies** to tackle innovation barriers.

ED Workshop PART II: Developing actionable project ideas

- **Narrowed the focus** to five priority areas: cross-regional collaboration, skills gaps, public procurement, financial support for startups, and innovation hubs.
- Participants developed **detailed project ideas** using structured templates.
- **Unanimous prioritization of Area 3: Address Skills Gaps**, reflecting the critical importance of building capacity and aligning skills with market needs.

The final outcome of workshops with proposed project ideas for cross-border collaboration areas identified:

- **Mentorship programmes:** Bridging skill gaps and aligning with market demands.
- **Micro-credentials:** Integrating industry insights into academic curricula to enhance workforce readiness.
- **Peer Learning and study visits:** Facilitating interregional knowledge exchange to boost ecosystem collaboration.

The key actionable project ideas:

- Creation of mentorship networks, targeted training programs, and cross-regional hubs.
- Leveraging financial tools such as innovation vouchers and public-private venture funds.

The ED Workshops successfully established a foundation for cross-regional collaboration and actionable project development within the **Cleantech sector**. By addressing skills gaps and fostering co-creative environments, the workshops set the stage for impactful initiatives under the EMPOWEREDbyNEIA project. The outcomes of the workshops will feed into a **Joint Action Plan**, to be delivered by the end of the project.

1. Introduction

The present document D.2.1 EDR Reports is the output of 'Task 2.1 – Entrepreneurial discovery workshops for identifying collaboration axis and opportunities' within work package 2 of the EMPOWEREDbyNEIA project. The purpose of this deliverable is to provide a comprehensive report on the Entrepreneurial Discovery Workshops conducted during the project phase. These workshops aimed to validate the findings from the previous analysis in WP1 and identify key macro themes through an interactive, collaborative approach involving stakeholders from seven European regional innovation ecosystems of consortium partners and our target involved in this project including: **Austria (Lower Austria), Bulgaria (Varna District), Croatia (Pannonian Croatia), Estonia (the entire country), Italy (Lazio region), Poland (Małopolska), and Romania (North-West Region).**

To achieve this, two online Entrepreneurial Discovery Workshops were organised, employing the Entrepreneurial Discovery Process methodology to encourage the development of ideas and collaboration opportunities.

This deliverable presents the outcomes of the Entrepreneurial Discovery (ED) Workshops. It outlines the primary purpose of the workshops, the methodology used, and a summary of the planning, participant selection and recruitment processes, as well as the discussions and outcomes of each workshop. The workshops focused on co-creating actionable solutions, which are presented as concrete project ideas to be incorporated into the co-design of the **Joint Action Plan**.

1.1 Background on the EMPOWEREDbyNEIA project

The European Innovation Policy encompasses a range of initiatives, instruments, and investments addressing diverse challenges, needs, and opportunities. However, regional disparities, territorial inequalities, and limited connectivity between ecosystems highlight the need for stronger synergies and policy coherence to better align sectoral priorities, policies, and key innovation players. To address these issues, the New European Innovation Agenda (NEIA) aims to unify and harmonize policies to accelerate the development and scaling of innovation across Europe.

Aligned with NEIA, the EMPOWEREDbyNEIA project—a Horizon Europe-funded initiative under the European Innovation Ecosystems initiative—seeks to empower regional innovation ecosystems by facilitating the emergence of collaborative, community-based activities and co-designing of Joint Action Plan. This project aims to enhance connections within European innovation systems while fostering policy alignment at the broader European level. Additionally, EMPOWEREDbyNEIA strengthens cooperation among quadruple helix stakeholders through an inclusive, gender-sensitive, mutual learning process at national and regional levels. It envisions shared tools and resources to support startups and scale-ups in driving innovation.

The EMPOWEREDbyNEIA consortium comprises a diverse group of venture accelerators, regional innovation and development agencies, and support organizations from seven European countries—Italy, Austria, Poland, Romania, Bulgaria, Croatia, and Estonia. The consortium's goal is to unite innovation ecosystem members across these regions, enabling them to identify the strengths, weaknesses, challenges, and gaps in each ecosystem. This collaboration aims to foster connections among key innovation actors, paving the way for implementing joint action plans. The project began in January 2024 and is set to conclude in December 2024.

1.2 Purpose and role of ED Workshops in project framework

The Entrepreneurial Discovery (ED) Workshops are designed to identify and foster collaborative opportunities within regional innovation ecosystems. The purpose of these workshops is to bring together key stakeholders from the quadruple helix—businesses, academia, government, and civil society—to co-create solutions that address regional challenges and support sustainable growth. By

leveraging the diverse expertise and perspectives of these stakeholders, ED Workshops aim to uncover strategic areas for collaboration, identify regional strengths and weaknesses, and generate actionable ideas that can be transformed into joint initiatives.

Additionally, the workshops delve into regional needs and challenges, generating ideas for potential solutions and supporting the development of cross-border collaborations. Based on topics identified through prior analysis, selected stakeholders will participate in brainstorming sessions to explore actionable solutions. The resulting macro perspective aims to connect regional innovation ecosystems and identify axes of potential collaboration. The collective outcomes of these workshops will contribute to WP3 activities on developing a tailored cross-border Joint Action Plan.

2. Methodology of the Entrepreneurial Discovery Workshops

2.1 Overview of the Entrepreneurial Discovery methodology applied

The methodological approach for the Entrepreneurial Discovery (ED) Workshops builds on the foundational mapping activities and SWOT analysis of each region conducted in WP1. Leveraging the EER (Entrepreneurial Ecosystem Research) methodology, the ED Workshops seek to identify opportunities for horizontal collaboration by defining key macro themes and collaboration axes with ecosystem stakeholders. These workshops promote an open exchange of ideas, fostering peer learning and discussion among participants. A central focus of this approach is the sharing of experiences within the consortium, enabling members to explore synergies and refine collaborative areas highlighted in the scoping note.

Widely used in regional innovation development initiatives, the EER methodology provides a structured framework for analysing, mapping, and strengthening regional entrepreneurial ecosystems. It emphasizes understanding ecosystem dynamics by examining interactions among key stakeholders, including businesses, government bodies, academic institutions, and civil society (the "quadruple helix" model). The main components of the EER methodology include ecosystem mapping, conducting SWOT analysis, identifying key themes and innovation sectors, and establishing cross-border and interregional connections to identify "horizontal collaboration axes"—all facilitated through the ED Workshops.

In the EMPOWEREDbyNEIA project, this approach was implemented in two online workshops involving regional innovation ecosystem stakeholders, innovation intermediaries, public authorities, and business support organizations. During the preparation phase, local challenges and opportunities coming from the output of WP1 were selected, along with key stakeholders and the best avenues for supporting solution ideas and future implementation. The outcomes of the two workshops informed the D2.2 Policy Brief and D3.1 Joint Action Plans, designed to support cross-regional projects requiring a multidisciplinary, collaborative approach.

2.2 Structure and process of ED Workshops

The Entrepreneurial Discovery (ED) Workshops were structured as two online sessions designed to engage Quadruple Helix (QH) stakeholders across the seven regions involved in the EMPOWEREDbyNEIA project. These stakeholders represented a balanced mix of academia, industry, government, and civil society, ensuring diverse perspectives and expertise. Each workshop was designed to foster active participation, with structured agendas that included presentations, thematic discussions, and interactive breakout sessions. The online format allowed for broad engagement, making it possible for stakeholders from all regions to join discussions, collaborate on regional challenges, and share insights without logistical barriers. Through targeted discussions and collaborative exercises, the workshops aimed to identify strategic opportunities, align on macro themes, and establish initial frameworks for cross-border collaboration, laying the groundwork for actionable joint projects and initiatives.

Each workshop was conducted online with a total duration of 2-3 hours, designed to maximize engagement and meaningful discussion within a focused timeframe. The goal was to recruit 15-25 participants for each session, ensuring a balanced representation from each Quadruple Helix (QH) category—academia, industry, government, and civil society. This selection strategy aimed to have at least one representative from each QH category across the seven regions: Lower Austria (Austria), Varna District (Bulgaria), Pannonian Croatia (Croatia), the entire country of Estonia, Lazio (Italy), Małopolska (Poland), and the North-West Region of Romania. By including diverse perspectives from each region, the workshops aimed to facilitate a comprehensive exchange of ideas and insights, allowing participants to collaboratively address regional challenges and identify strategic opportunities for cross-border collaboration.

2.3 Selection and recruitment of participants

During the selection and recruitment phase, project partners were provided with an email template to invite their region key stakeholders effectively. An online registration form was also made available to streamline and simplify the process. Upon registration, participants received a confirmation email containing the invitation link, workshop instructions, and a detailed agenda, ensuring they were well-prepared for the session.

2.4 Digital tools and platforms used

The workshops were conducted online using the [Zoom](#) platform, chosen for its user-friendly interface and broad familiarity among participants. For interactive sessions, participants were divided into breakout rooms, each facilitated by an appointed moderator to guide the discussion and ensure a smooth exchange of ideas. Additionally, the [Miro](#) platform was used to enhance collaboration. Miro, a virtual whiteboard tool, enables real-time teamwork and is ideal for brainstorming, planning, and interactive workshops. Its features allowed participants to create, organize, and share ideas visually, making the sessions both engaging and productive.

3. ED Workshop PART I: Foundation for collaboration

3.1 Workshop objectives and goals

The aim of **ED Workshop PART I** was to foster collaboration and co-design across European regional innovation ecosystems in the Cleantech sector. The workshop sought to ignite innovation and collaboration by identifying cross-border collaboration opportunities, exploring thematic areas for innovation, and charting a sustainable roadmap for the Cleantech sector. By bringing together stakeholders from academia, industry, government, and the public sector, the workshop provided a dynamic platform for dialogue, ideation, and actionable insights.

The operational goal of **ED Workshop PART I** was to identify opportunities and ideas for cross-border collaboration and the development of joint projects. Additionally, it aimed to understand the main needs and demands of participants within this sector, serving as a foundational step for shaping the concept and focus of **ED Workshop PART II**.

3.2 Planning and organisation

The ED Workshop PART I was planned on **10th July 2024 from 10:00 to 12:30 CET**. An invitation mail was prepared for consortium partners to invite the stakeholders of their ecosystems, particularly the ones who were interviewed for the WP1 purpose (**Annex 1**). ED Workshops were planned to be carried out on **Zoom** and for ED discussion, to use the **Miro Board** tool. The workshop was scheduled for two hours. This length of the online event seemed to be a compromise between the possibility of a more in-depth interaction and maintaining the attention of participants from different countries and backgrounds.

Figure 1: ED Workshop PART I banner

Since the workshop was planned only in English Language, they were required to have a good command of English, being the common communication language for the partner countries. It should be noted that English was not the native language of any of the project partners and that no project partners share a common language. Simultaneous translations were not planned due to the risk of unnecessary prolongation of the event, communication problems. However, the event organisers were aware that the requirement of fluent English could eliminate some professionals and experts who did not have the necessary language skills. The table below shows the agenda of the ED Workshop PART I.

Table 1: ED Workshop PART I Agenda

Time	Agenda	Speaker
10:00 - 10:05	Welcome and Introduction	Romana Toft & Anna sowa-jadczyk, (MARR SA/Poland)
10:05 - 10:15	Presentation of EMPOWEREDbyNEIA project	Fahimeh Mousavi, Project Coordinator (INNOVA/Italy)
10:15 - 10:30	Introducing the quadruple helix concept and Entrepreneurial Discovery based on a case study	Monika Machowska, Deputy Director (KPT/Poland)
10:30 - 10:45	Presenting the SWOT analysis of seven European ecosystems on Cleantech domain	Julia Bauer, Project Manager (ACCENT/Austria)
10:45 – 11:15	Breakout sessions on exploring collaboration areas and action plans	All participants
11:15 - 11:40	Plenary presentation of breakout sessions’ results	Rappeartures/Moderators
11:40 - 12:00	Next steps - Collection of inputs/feedback for Workshop PART II	Fahimeh Mousavi, Project Coordinator (INNOVA/Italy) Monika Machowska, Deputy Director (KPT/Poland)
12:00	Closing remarks	Fahimeh Mousavi, Project Coordinator (INNOVA/Italy)

3.3 Participants and QH representatives

Participants of the **ED Workshop PART I** were recruited based on the objectives of the EMPOWEREDbyNEIA project and included representatives of the Quadruple Helix ecosystems from seven European countries, the project partners. The recruitment of the participants took place through a registration form EU Survey ([EU survey registration form](#)).

Preferred participants: The participants of the ED workshop(s) were to be recruited first of all from the professionals/experts interviewed by the partners for the SWOT and GAP analyses (interviews carried out by the partners in the previous task). The partners were required to inform the participants they should attend the ED workshop part 2 as the continuation. 2. Role of partners in the recruitment process: Each project partner was required to carry out the recruitment process in their respective country and provide at least 1 representative from each category of the QH, including (if possible) a representative of a start-up co-funded by a woman.

The workshop was planned for a minimum of 15 up to 25 participants (in conformity with the project objectives), but the organisers were open to larger numbers of attendees. The project partners were required to appoint at least 1 partner representative to attend the workshop. The addressed industries (for the Business/Industry category of the QH) were cleantech, green tech, if possible. The two tables below present the data on participants by QH category and country.

Table 2: ED Workshop PART I data on participants by QH category

Quadruple Helix category	Invited	Registered
Academia/Research Institutions	11	7
Government/Public Sector	12	6
Industry/Business	17	14
Civil Society	5	4
Partners and Moderators	16	16
TOTAL Participants	61	47
TOTAL Quadruple Helix representatives	47	31

Table 3: ED Workshop PART I data on participants by country

Country	Academia	Government	Industry	Civil Society	Partners & Moderators	Total Participants
Austria	2	1	2	0	2	7
Bulgaria	0	0	1	1	1	3
Croatia	1	0	1	2	3	7
Estonia	0	0	1	0	1	2
Italy	2	1	2	1	3	9
Poland	1	3	2	0	4	10
Romania	1	1	5	0	2	9
TOTAL	7	6	14	4	15	47

3.4 Workshop course and methodology

Roma Toft from MARR SA, Poland, welcomed the participants and shortly introduced the partners of the project by country and institution, especially MARR SA, responsible for the organisation of the ED workshop(s), moderators, and guests of the event – representatives of local innovation ecosystems. Next, Fahimeh Mousavi from INNOVA, Italy, presented the overview of the EMPOWEREDbyNEIA project, its objectives, goals, and expected effects (results, products).

After the presentation of the project, Monika Machowska and Urszula Woźniak, ED experts representing MARR SA, made an overview of the quadruple helix stakeholder concept and Entrepreneurial Discovery process, explaining what it is, giving some examples of their previous ED events, and clarifying the role of the participants in the present ED workshop.

Then, Julia Bauer from ACCENT, Austria, presented the conclusions of the SWOT and GAP analyses on seven ecosystems in the regions participating in the EMPOWEREDbyNEIA project. The goal of the presentation was to get the participants familiar with the main strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats of the QH ecosystems identified in each of the participating regions/countries during the previous stage of the project. Knowledge of differences and similarities, needs, challenges, barriers, and successes (best practices) was to facilitate the identification of common problems to overcome,

best practices to share, and failures to avoid – and to help work out ideas for joint, interregional, and intersectoral collaboration projects.

After the presentation on the SWOT and GAP analyses, the main part of the workshop started. It had a form of moderated roundtable discussions. The participants and partners were pre-assigned to 4 breakout rooms. The groups were roughly similar in number and consisted of representatives of various QH categories and partner countries. Each group worked with the use of the Miro Board tool and was moderated by one of the appointed moderators.

Before the participants moved to their breakout rooms, Urszula Woźniak (MARR SA, Poland) made a short introduction to the workshop methodology and rules and presented the objectives of the discussion to be carried out in each of the breakout rooms. She also explained how the Miro Board works since not every participant was familiar with this tool. During the session with the Miro Boards, representatives of various QH categories were asked to use different colour post-it notes for the respective category (for instance: Government – **green**, Academia – **yellow**, Industry/Business – **pink**, Civil Society - **blue**).

Each group was to refer to **4 questions/issues** (that were supposed to support project partners in developing the agenda for the next part of the workshop). The Miro Board discussion was supposed to be an inspirational session offering time and space for sharing participants' ideas, opinions, and experiences. For better reference to points presented in the breakout room discussions, the participants were asked to identify the region they represent (not always they did it). 4 Breakout rooms: in each room the following questions were asked:

1. **Question 1:** What initiative, project, or best practice has successfully encouraged innovation in your ecosystem?
2. **Question 2:** What are the main needs in your sector hindering innovation adoption?
3. **Question 3:** How can government policies and funding better support new opportunities for innovation?
4. **Question 4:** Please provide 3-5 (or more) recommendations for steps/topics to address the innovation challenges you region is facing.

Each session in the four breakout rooms was scheduled to last 30 minutes. Following the sessions, an appointed representative from each group provided a brief presentation summarizing the group's findings. Below is a record of the key findings from the four discussion groups (breakout rooms). The following entries are slightly edited statements (quotes) from individual participants, as documented on the Miro Boards in each breakout room. Additionally, a color-coding system was used for each QH category (post-it notes) to make it easier to distinguish between respondents.

BREAKOUT ROOM 1

Moderator: Monika Machowska

Each QH categories answered the question one as it follows:

Q1. What initiative, project, or best practice has successfully encouraged innovation in your ecosystem?

Industry

- The development of the *Center of Excellence for Furniture* (with the collaboration of 5 companies and 1 cluster) – an investment that will further provide innovative services for the furniture/manufacturing industry at the regional level (based in Cluj-Napoca) (infrastructure and support services for companies that wish to invest).
- At the regional level, there are many initiatives to facilitate innovation challenges and open innovation sessions, startup competitions involving researchers, acceleration programmes and dynamic living labs. Also, regional public venture capital funds have been launched to support high-tech venture creation or consolidation.
- Support of the development of innovation ecosystems on the international scope by promoting meetings between supply and demand sides for innovation.
- Industry-Academia collaboration in skills development and upskilling and reskilling of personnel.
- Connecting the demand and the offer (supply) for innovation and digitalization services through financial support and consultancy (financed by the EC for now).

Government

- Govtech innovations for local governments: facilitate the cooperation between innovators and local governments.

Academia

- Open Innovation Hubs are definitely the best practice initiative that encourages networks and, in consequence, successful collaboration within innovation ecosystems (industries, academia, governments, citizens).

Civil Society

- Involvement of Technology Transfer Centres.

Q2: What are the main needs in your sector hindering innovation adoption?

Industry

- Limited access to funding OR complicated administrative needs/requests; the need for

information and “translation” of the current information/methodologies.

- Less fragmented ecosystem of multiple actors.
- More targeted public and private innovation funds for SMEs on specific verticals (e.g., cleantech).
- More effective support of technology transfer offices (centres) to boost research results towards the market.
- More favourable conditions for young entrepreneurial ideas (tax incentives, subsidised loans, training for entrepreneurial team formation).
- Spreading the culture of innovation as the driving force of the new economy.

Government

- Better cooperation between the academia and business sectors – more joint pilot projects.
- Better cooperation within a given innovation ecosystem (public authorities, private sector, IOB, industry, academia, civil society).

Academia

- Many initiatives have been launched lately; however, additional resources/budget would raise the number of activities.
- Broad understanding across diverse stakeholders of the advantages of open innovation that will lead to knowledge transfer.

Civil Society

- Better connections within ecosystems to establish closer relationships between different players in each ecosystem.
- Better access to finance and financial support.

Q3: How can government policies and funding better support new opportunities for innovation?

Industry

- A more clear and long-term support framework.
- More support measures tailored to the specific needs of SMEs and micro-sized companies, including a less complex application system (for funds).
- More support schemes to boost technology transfer.

Government

- More joint pilot projects for representatives of quadruple helix categories even for small projects) – to practice various solutions before carried out to a bigger scale.
- RIS3 Strategy & Smart Specialisation Platforms.

Q4: Please provide 3-5 (or more) recommendations for steps/topics to address the innovation challenges your region is facing.

Industry

- Increased focus on innovative & sustainable products/services through direct funding of RDI.
- Promotion of good practices of different natures for “inspiration”.
- Staff exchange programmes for best practices adoption and dissemination.
- More Workshops like this – with a close follow-up on action plans and their implementation.
- Create a more cohesive and unified support system to overcome fragmentation of actors, measures, and schemes.
- Adopt a long-term strategy with clear priority in vertical areas.

- More focus on sustainability and cleantech.
- Invest in training initiatives to boost innovative entrepreneurship and provide expert mentorship, access to investor networks, and tailored business coaching services.
- Increase communication and collaboration among innovation actors.
- Support collaboration between institutions, academia, and businesses with a view to derisking
- More dedicated programmes to improve valorisation of high-value knowledge and IP at the educational level and R&D institutions in the region, especially in the cleantech sector.
- Sustaining and developing the research and innovation capacities and adapting advanced technologies.
- Productive investments to improve the competitiveness of SMEs.

Government

- Organisation of a set of meetings that will let different types of actors/stakeholders work together effectively and exchange experience, good practices, and ideas (development of smart labs).
- More joint pilot projects for representatives of quadruple helix categories even in small projects to practice various solutions before implementing larger scale initiatives.

Academia

- Clear, possibly Europe-wide standardised process, guidelines, and rules when it comes to IP rights.
- Broader communication concerning the advantages of innovation ecosystems for diverse stakeholders (especially local governmental structures) is needed.

BREAKOUT ROOM 2

Moderator: Fahimeh Mousavi

Q1. What initiative, project, or best practice has successfully encouraged innovation in your ecosystem?

Industry

- CleanTech Accelerator in Romania (Techcelerator.Co/cleantech).
- Food waste project in Romania.

Government

- Spin-off strategy - how to get research go to market.

Civil Society

- EIT Food Hub Bulgaria 2023 is organising initiatives to support innovation in the agricultural industry (agrifood).

Q2: What are the main needs in your sector hindering innovation adoption?

Industry

- Facilitate access to public funds for start-ups in Italy.
- Brain drains in Romania.

Government

- In Austria, from the perspective of scientists: less administration process, for start-ups: awareness of failure exists, but its perception from society is not acceptable, From the perspective of investors: 100% commitment to start-up projects.
- Government policies in terms of public-private investments in Romania.
- Public procurement regulations specific for innovation/innovative projects in Romania.

Q3: How can government policies and funding better support new opportunities for innovation?

Industry

- Less paperwork.
- Less administration work for companies.

Government

- Innovation should become part of policies in a practical way.
- Lack of implementation of tools/methods provided through EU policies.

Q4: Please provide 3-5 (or more) recommendations for steps/topics to address the innovation challenges you region is facing.

Industry

- Better business models for startups and Spinoffs.
- Support for validation of business models for international markets.

Government

- Founders should focus more on validating the business models for international scale.
- Licensing issues and fees.

Academia

- IP management and protection issues for early-stage startups and innovative researchers.

BREAKOUT ROOM 3

Moderator: Urszula Woźniak

Q1. What initiative, project, or best practice has successfully encouraged innovation in your ecosystem?

Industry

- The EUDIS hackathon supports innovation in the European defence sector¹.
- Co-working spaces and side events: Latitude59.
- B2B green Platform - Greene 4.0 project, Interreg Central Europe Programme
- The best practice that I want to share is a specific policy (Brevetti+ / Patents +) to intellectual property to foster the protection of any useful result of cleantech research activity that has value, including know-how.

Government

- Grants for innovation RUP²
- Networking and mapping of innovations and best practices.
- Rosewood Network³: NOTE: Competence Centre Ltd. is a business support organisation owned by the Regional Authority.

Academia

- Competition for innovation⁴
- The initiatives in our ecosystem are scarce and sparse; support is available through local clusters and ERDF funding, but no landmark Cleantech project exists.

Q2: What are the main needs in your sector hindering innovation adoption?

Industry

- Skills improvement, practical training – to have the same knowledge in the regions
- Policy strategies to support Cleantech demonstration, encouraging active participation of the private sector, using

¹ <https://www.tehnpol.ee/eudis-hakaton-toetab-innovatsiooni-euroopa-kaitsektoris/>

² <https://eis.ee/en/grants/programme-for-applied-research/>

³ <https://rosewood-network.eu/>

⁴ <https://ajujah.t.ee/>

targeted financing mechanisms (tax credit) to de-risk first commercial projects, developing enabling test and measurement cleantech infrastructure, green public procurement, and responsive regulation.

- Talent Development: Programs to attract and retain top talent in the cleantech sector.

Government

- Better connection, understanding, and cooperation between industry, academia, and the public sector.
- Public support to access to finance.

Academia

- Access to funding.

Civil Society

- Needs refer to better cooperation between innovation actors, access to financing, green infrastructure, etc. (NGOs).

Q3: How can government policies and funding better support new opportunities for innovation?

Industry

- Government strategies are expected to increase the early-stage innovation supply by establishing a national entity dedicated to cleantech innovation and setting long-term policy indications and priorities.
- Supporting cleantech R&D funding and matching it with national climate and innovation priorities.
- Encouraging intra-governmental coordination on innovation, educating future innovators, and developing measures to attract international talents.

Government

- Simplifying regulations.
- Increased funding for research and

development in cleantech sectors would stimulate innovation.

- Less administrative burden
- Faster access to funding
- Government-backed platform for facilitation of collaboration between stakeholders.
- Listen to the needs expressed by academia and industry experts, as well as private investors in the region, and integrate them into bottom-up policymaking.

Q4: Please provide 3-5 (or more) recommendations for steps/topics to address the innovation challenges your region is facing.

Government

- There is a need to design a multi-regional policy formulation: the scheme should be standardized to develop a national/regional Cleantech Innovation Scheme to support prototypes, the launch and growth of cleantech start-ups, but also proof of concept incentive schemes to validate innovative research ideas for connecting local academia and business actors to perform collaborative research.
- Government-backed platform for collaboration between different stakeholders.
- Regarding government strategies: The brunt of the dirty technology is mostly felt by the public first. There should be a government-enforced pathway for following public complaints regarding pollution. Early warnings, investigation of complaints, etc. This would create an atmosphere of urgency towards cleantech solutions.
- Increase funding for research and development specific to the cleantech sector.

General

- 1) Set up a structured scouting process to identify the best companies and most promising projects contributing to the Regional S3.
- 2) Align public and private investments to create leverage effects and accelerate the development of projects and growth of companies.
- 3) Catalyse the forces of all ecosystem stakeholders through dedicated monitoring tools and support instruments.

BREAKOUT ROOM 4

Moderator: Christopher Opancar

Q1. What initiative, project, or best practice has successfully encouraged innovation in your ecosystem?

Industry

- OPEN ITALY programme: Large Companies Business Needs and Startups solutions. 12 weeks PoC. Test innovative solutions before investing. Create an ecosystem platform in which corporations share their business needs and startups can solve them with their solutions.
- Multistakeholder cooperation.

Government

- Lower Austrian Programme Innovation Ecosystem financing facilitation of networking (Clusters, Technopoles, Platforms).
- Innovation procurement support (www.ioeb.at).

Academia

- “Be the Role Model” competition: promotion of innovative project ideas at the international level and evaluation of innovations by an international jury.
- Public funding programs: proof of concept for the SME sector and research organisations. International development of networks like EU projects: Enterprise Europe Network, KET4CP.
- EVENTS - R&D, entrepreneurial, commercialization of research, res networks bottom-up.

Q2: What are the main needs in your sector hindering innovation adoption?

Industry

- The speed at which startups operate in comparison to large corporate organizations (lack of entrepreneurial culture).
- The absence of open innovation departments in all of the large companies (only R&D departments with different strategic logic).
- The IT industry digitalises other regions, not local.
- Match supply and needs (e.g., innovation procurement).

Government

- Laws and regulations are not helpful.

Academia

- Lack of regulatory framework regarding spin-off/spin-out university-based entities; no spin-off tradition.
- No registry or database of available resources regarding the academia sector (expertise, knowledge, IP, labs, equipment).
- The academia sector is working for innovations - easier abroad.
- Lack of long-term perspectives for innovation and commercialization in the academia sector.
- Lack of long-term financing for innovation projects.
- General lack of practical experience in conducting innovative processes (lacking skills).

Q3: How can government policies and funding better support new opportunities for innovation?

Industry

- Establishing or supporting venture capital funds that focus on early-stage startups.
- Providing more guarantees for loans to innovative businesses.
- Creating institutional hubs where businesses, researchers, and policymakers can collaborate.

Government

- Developing tools for the evaluation of the quality
- Accountability, sustainability of support.

Academia

- Support through long-term programmes and clear organisation.
- To develop a regulatory framework regarding spin-off/spin-out university-based entities and commercialization of innovations.
- New open calls to connect the private sector and academia.

Q4: Please provide 3-5 (or more) recommendations for steps/topics to address the innovation challenges you region is facing.

Industry

- Increase VB and CVB approaches.
- Connection of the national ecosystem with the European ecosystems.

Government

- Sharing practices among regions.
- Focus on challenge-driven innovation: what we do in the region (industry, academia, policy makers, civil society) and what we want to solve.

Academia

- Provide funding for BSO and TTO to provide services in the technology transfer process.
- Develop business support organizations and TTOs with knowledge and expertise.
- Combining research teams
- Development of university resource pool
- National financial support for innovation.

At the end of the session, all participants were returned back to the main room and were asked to answer the main final question:

Question 5: Please provide at least 1 specific action plan to support the implementation of cross-regional project ideas.

The table below summarizes the key findings and recommendations from each breakout rooms.

Table 4: ED Workshop PART I key findings and recommendations per breakout room

Breakout Room 1	
Questions	Key recommendations
<p>Q1: What initiative, project, or best practice has successfully encouraged innovation in your ecosystem?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participants emphasized collaboration between academia and industry for upskilling. Government initiatives supporting tech innovation and technology transfer centres were highlighted. Open innovation hubs bridging research, industry, and the public sector were recognized as key drivers.
<p>Q2: What are the main needs in your sector hindering innovation adoption?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Limited funding and financial support. Need for better collaboration between academia and business. Better connected ecosystems to foster relationships between innovation stakeholders.
<p>Q3: How can government policies and funding better support new opportunities for innovation?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Joint pilot projects were recommended to experiment with innovative solutions. Clearer support frameworks for SMEs and support for technology transfer.
<p>Q4: Please provide 3-5 (or more) recommendations for steps/topics to</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> More pilot projects for scalable innovation.

<i>address the innovation challenges you region is facing.</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Support for research capacities and collaboration between institutions. – Develop clear IP guidelines to facilitate innovation.
Breakout Room 2	
Questions	Key recommendations
Q1: <i>What initiative, project, or best practice has successfully encouraged innovation in your ecosystem?</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Focused on tech accelerators (like the Cleantech Accelerator in Romania) and food waste projects to drive innovation. – Regional initiatives supporting agrifood innovation were also highlighted.
Q2: <i>What are the main needs in your sector hindering innovation adoption?</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Brain drains as a significant issue. – Need for better access to public funding and more supportive governmental policies for innovation.
Q3: <i>How can government policies and funding better support new opportunities for innovation?</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Reducing administrative barriers and making policies more practical. – Better implementation of EU tools and methods.
Q4: <i>Please provide 3-5 (or more) recommendations for steps/topics to address the innovation challenges you region is facing.</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Developing better business models for startups. – Addressing licensing issues and validating business models for international markets key priorities.
Breakout Room 3	
Questions	Key recommendations
Q1: <i>What initiative, project, or best practice has successfully encouraged innovation in your ecosystem?</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Co-working spaces and platforms for collaboration as vital innovation enablers. – Funding opportunities through regional innovation platforms crucial for growth.
Q2: <i>What are the main needs in your sector hindering innovation adoption?</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Skills development and practical training. – Better coordination between industry, academia, and the public sector.
Q3: <i>How can government policies and funding better support new opportunities for innovation?</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Recommendations for simplifying regulations and reducing administrative burdens. – Increased R&D funding and government-backed collaboration platforms.
Q4: <i>Please provide 3-5 (or more) recommendations for steps/topics to address the innovation challenges you region is facing.</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Focused on setting up a scouting process to identify key projects. – Aligning public and private investments to accelerate project development and growth.
Breakout Room 4	
Questions	Key recommendations
Q1: <i>What initiative, project, or best practice has successfully encouraged innovation in your ecosystem?</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Absence of open innovation departments in larger companies. – Focused on the need to match supply and demand for innovation solutions. – The need for long-term financing and regulatory frameworks for spin-offs.
Q2: <i>What are the main needs in your sector hindering innovation adoption?</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – The speed and agility of startups vs large organizations as a barrier. – Lack of long-term financing and infrastructure to support innovation projects.
Q3: <i>How can government policies and funding better support new opportunities for innovation?</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – More use/facility of access to Venture capital funds to support early-stage startups. – Need for more guarantees for loans to innovative businesses and developing institutional hubs for collaboration.
Q4: <i>Please provide 3-5 (or more) recommendations for steps/topics to address the innovation challenges you region is facing.</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Increase cross-industry sharing practices and create national resource pools.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Establish a cross-regional acceleration program for Cleantech solutions and provide financial support for technology transfer.
Main Room	
<p>Main final question: <i>Please provide at least 1 specific action plan to support the implementation of cross-regional project ideas.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Establishing cross-industry sharing practices and a European Cleantech alliance. – Creating innovation hubs or Centres of Excellence to connect regions. – Pilot projects to match challenges in one region with solutions from another. – Increasing knowledge sharing and mobilizing cross-regional networks for collaborative innovation.

3.5 Conclusions and lessons learned

As a result of discussions held in differentiated contexts (breakout rooms with representatives from various Quadruple Helix (QH) categories and countries), several key needs and demands emerged. These insights serve as recommendations for improvement and collaboration areas to be addressed when developing joint projects:

- 1) **Enhanced access to funding sources.** The need for more accessible funding mechanisms was highlighted. Barriers such as complex procedures, unclear objectives, and inadequate dissemination of information should be addressed to better align funding opportunities with the needs of potential beneficiaries.
- 2) **Excessive administrative procedures that hinder the development of innovation.** There is a strong demand to simplify administrative procedures that currently impede innovation development. Reducing paperwork and streamlining processes across different levels, contexts, and sectors can significantly enhance efficiency.
- 3) **Improved validation of business models for startups and spinoffs.** Refining and supporting the validation processes for business models is critical for the success of startups and spinoffs. Tailored, streamlined, and effective validation frameworks can significantly enhance their competitiveness, reduce the risk of failure, and equip them to succeed in both national and international markets. Achieving this requires robust collaboration among Quadruple Helix stakeholders across regions to ensure the models are well-adapted to diverse contexts and needs.
- 4) **Promotion of best practices in innovation development.** A consistent and holistic system to create, share, and promote best practices in innovation development across European regions were called for. Suggested initiatives include pilot projects, exchange programmes, workshops, and action plan models, involving all quadruple helix stakeholders to foster learning and collaboration.
- 5) **Long-term collaboration strategies among key actors of innovation ecosystems.** The need for robust, long-term strategies to support sustainable collaboration among innovation ecosystem actors were expressed. Current strategies, which tend to be short-or mid-term, limit opportunities for planning long-term investments and partnerships.
- 6) **Improved public procurement regulations for innovations.** There is a need to adapt public procurement frameworks to better support the requirements of innovators and align them with market realities, fostering an environment conducive to innovation.

- 7) **Customized support systems for startups and spinoffs.** The need for tailored support systems that cater to the unique challenges faced by startups and university-based spinoffs. This includes tolerance for failure, acknowledgment of differences between researchers and entrepreneurs, and revisions to licensing and fee structures.
- 8) **Revaluation of regulations and funding mechanisms.** The importance of reassessing existing laws, regulations, programmes, strategies, and funding mechanisms for quality, effectiveness, and sustainability. Greater clarity about the impact and reliability of both private and public funding sources is necessary.
- 9) **Unified framework for interregional collaboration.** A common framework is needed to support the development of cleantech solutions. Current efforts are fragmented, with diverse schemes creating inconsistencies and inefficiencies.

While these recommendations were derived from rich discussions, the workshop also faced some issues that had to be tackled during the workshop:

- 1) **Language Barriers:** English, as a second language for all participants, presented potential risks of miscommunication.
- 2) **Time Constraints:** Balancing the need for comprehensive discussions with the time limitations typical of online workshops required careful compromise.
- 3) **Diverse Perspectives:** Participants represented a wide array of cultures, experiences, and professional backgrounds (spanning quadruple helix stakeholders of each ecosystem from seven European countries), which enriched the dialogue but required effort to align differing viewpoints.

Key Lessons for PART II Implementation:

The needs, demands, and recommendations identified helped for the planning of subsequent phases, ensuring that future efforts address these collaboration axes and improvement areas effectively.

4. ED Workshop PART II: Developing actionable project ideas

4.1 Workshop objectives and goals

During ED Workshop PART I, participants provided valuable insights, identifying obstacles and challenges that hinder innovation adoption across regions. These discussions shed light on the key strengths and weaknesses within innovation ecosystems, along with opportunities for improvement. The outcomes of PART I underscored the importance of stronger collaboration and highlighted several critical areas for cross-regional partnerships to advance innovation. In PART II, the workshop focused on:

- Exploring innovative ideas for future joint projects aimed at fostering sustainable growth.
- Identifying collaboration areas and actionable solutions for implementing joint project ideas.

The primary operational goal of ED Workshop PART II was to refine five project ideas derived from the common challenges identified in PART I. These ideas were further developed into objectives for collaborative projects to be pursued in the next phase of the EMPOWEREDbyNEIA initiative and beyond.

Additionally, this workshop aimed to unite stakeholders from academia, industry, government, and the public sector, fostering a co-creative environment to develop solutions addressing the challenges and opportunities identified earlier in the year.

4.2 Planning and organisation

The **ED Workshop PART II** took place on **22nd October 2024, from 10:00 to 12:00 CET**. An invitation mail template was shared with partners, enabling them to invite key stakeholders from their ecosystems to the workshop.

Figure 2: ED Workshop PART II banner

The banner features the EMPOWERED by NEIA logo on the left. The main text reads "Entrepreneurial Discovery Workshop PART II" in large white font. Below this, it states "Fostering co-design Collaboration approach within EU Regional Innovation Ecosystems focusing on Cleantech." On the right, a green box highlights the date "22nd October 2024", and below it, "ZOOM LIVE STREAMING 10:00 until 12:30 (CET)". A "REGISTER NOW" button with a QR code is also present. The bottom of the banner displays logos for INNOIA, Venture Booster, ac/cent, tero, mARR, RAPIV, and BEAMLINE ACCELERATOR. A central image shows hands holding a green globe.

Special attention was given to engaging those who participated in PART I, offering them an opportunity to share their solutions to the challenges they previously identified. The invitation mail template is annexed for reference (**Annex 2**). The workshop was conducted using the Zoom platform, with a Miro

board facilitating interactive activities where participants collaboratively defined solutions for the identified areas. The event was scheduled for two and half hours, striking a balance between allowing in-depth discussions and maintaining the engagement of participants. The agenda of the event is illustrated in the figure and table below, outlining the session's structure.

Figure 3: ED Workshop PART II agenda

Table 5: ED Workshop PART II agenda

Time	Agenda	Speaker
10:00 - 10:15	Welcome and Introduction	Romana Toft & Anna sowa-jadczyk, (MARR SA/Poland)
10:15 - 10:30	Summary of key findings from ED Workshop PART I	Fahimeh Mousavi, Project Coordinator (INNOVA/Italy)
10:30 - 10:40	Breakout rooms formation & instructions	Urszula Wozniak, (KPT/Poland)
10:40 - 11:55	Breakout rooms: – roundtable discussions on ideas for joint projects	All participants
11:55 – 12:20	Roundtable presentations: – overview of proposed solutions	Rappeartures/Moderators
12:20 - 12:25	Next steps	Fahimeh Mousavi, Project Coordinator (INNOVA/Italy)
12:25 - 12:30	Wrap-up and closing	Fahimeh Mousavi, Project Coordinator (INNOVA/Italy)

4.3 Participants and QH representatives

Participants for the **ED Workshop PART II** were selected in alignment with the objectives of the EMPOWEREDbyNEIA project. They included representatives from Quadruple Helix (QH) ecosystems across seven European countries of project partners. The recruitment process mirrored that of **PART I** and was conducted through a registration form hosted on EU Survey (the survey form is annexed as Annex 4).

Priority was given to recruiting participants who had attended **PART I**, providing continuity and an opportunity to build on previously identified challenges. However, the workshop was also open to the public, welcoming new participants to enrich the discussions with fresh perspectives. The tables below provide an overview of participant data, categorized by QH sector and country (excluding moderators and project partner representatives).

Table 6: ED Workshop PART II data on participants by QH category

Quadruple helix (QH) category	Registered
Academia/Research Institutions	10
Government/Public Sector	5
Industry/Business	15
Civil Society	1
TOTAL participants (excluding moderators and partners)	31

Table 7: Table 3: ED Workshop PART II data on participants by country

Country	Academia	Government	Industry	Civil Society	Total Quadruple helix representatives
Austria	2	1	2	-	5
Bulgaria	1	-	-	-	1
Croatia	1	-	5	1	7
Estonia	1	-	4	-	5
Italy	2	1	1	-	4
Poland	2	-	2	-	4
Romania	1	2	1	-	4
Turkey	-	1	-	-	1
TOTAL	10	5	15	1	31

4.4 Workshop course and methodology

The **ED Workshop PART II** commenced with an introduction by **Roma Toft from MARR SA, Poland**, the partner responsible for the implementation of the ED Workshops under the EMPOWEREDbyNEIA project. Roma welcomed the participants and provided a brief introduction to the project partners by country and institution. She also acknowledged the moderators and guests, particularly the representatives of local innovation ecosystems.

Following the introduction, **the Project Coordinator, Fahimeh Mousavi from INNOVA, Italy**, delivered a concise overview of the EMPOWEREDbyNEIA project. She highlighted the key findings and outcomes from **ED Workshop PART I** and outlined the main objectives for **PART II**, setting the stage for the day's activities.

Next, **Urszula Woźniak from KPT, Poland**, provided participants with a detailed overview of the workshop structure, along with instructions on how to use the Miro board. She clarified the expectations for participant engagement and explained how the Miro board would facilitate collaborative activities.

The core segment of the workshop then began, consisting of moderated roundtable discussions. Participants were divided into three breakout rooms, each led by an appointed moderator:

- **Breakout room 1: Urszula Woźniak (KPT, Poland)**
- **Breakout room 2: Agnieszka Włodarczyk (KPT, Poland)**
- **Breakout room 3: Julia Bauer (Accent, Austria)**

To ensure a balanced and diverse exchange of ideas, participants were preassigned to breakout rooms. The allocation ensured representation from various QH categories and partner countries, fostering a rich, multidisciplinary dialogue.

Within their breakout rooms, participants worked collaboratively using the Miro board tool under the guidance of the moderators. This structure ensured productive discussions, and the generation of actionable solutions aligned with the workshop's objectives.

Given the limited duration of the workshop and the recognition that some key collaboration areas identified in ED Workshop PART I (see Section 3.5) require a more extensive, long-term strategic approach, it was decided to narrow the focus to five priority areas from the nine initially identified. This selective approach ensured that meaningful solutions could be developed within the available time frame. The following **five key areas** were selected for focused discussion and solution development:

- **Area 1 - Promote cross-regional collaboration:** Create platforms that facilitate collaboration between European regions, including sharing knowledge and best practices, in order to address innovation divide.
- **Area 2 - Support startups and spinoffs with financial instruments.** Focus on providing venture capital, loans, and public funding mechanisms that target early-stage innovation.
- **Area 3 - Address skills gaps:** prioritise upskilling through training programmes that align with market needs, particularly for SMEs and Cleantech innovators.
- **Area 4 - Inadequate public procurement regulations for innovations:** Adjusted to the needs of innovators and the market.
- **Area 5 - Develop innovation hubs:** Set up cross-regional hubs or centres of excellence to foster collaboration, facilitate project development, and provide shared resources.

After providing instructions and presenting the selected collaboration areas to the participants, they were assigned to their respective breakout rooms, and the interactive sessions began. These sessions were structured into three distinct phases:

PHASE I of the Breakout rooms

BRAINSTORMING SESSION (30 Minutes)

In the initial phase of the workshop, participants worked individually to brainstorm and document at least two potential solutions for the selected collaboration areas. The results of this individual work are summarized below (with minor edits for clarity). Additionally, the provided screenshots illustrate the outcome of the subsequent voting phase (PHASE II), where participants identified the highest-priority solutions using green dots.

BREAKOUT ROOM 1

Moderator: Urszula Woźniak

Figure 4: ED Workshop PART II breakout room 1 solutions

For Area 1 - Promoting Cross-Regional Collaboration, the proposed solutions were as follows:

- Create direct cooperation among existing **cleantech clusters** and create a common platform for this cooperation (*established under the EMPOWEREDbyNEIA project*).
- Participate in common applications under different EU calls.
- Organize an **awareness-raising campaign** on Cleantech sector.
- Develop a **matching platform** for technology offers and requests to allow cross-border technology transfer in the cleantech field.
- Find common topics for cooperation among cluster members.
- Create **cooperation possibilities** on two levels: 1) cooperation among clusters, 2) cooperation among cluster members (companies, organizations, and so on).
- Create **cross-industry collaboration and events with industry and academia**.
- It is necessary to consistently support organizations that foster collaboration, such as EIT (Innoenergy, etc.), to ensure their activities are sustainable.

For Area 2 - Support startups and spinoffs with financial instruments, proposed solutions included:

- Create **public-private venture fund** for early-stage green tech and digital startups.
- Implement an **educational scheme** to help startups develop effective business cases (*models*) and learn (*from each other*) about the selection criteria for investment used by investors.
- Organize events to educate start-ups on **funding opportunities** and teach them how to approach funding organizations.
- Promote and raise awareness about **EIC (European Innovation Council) funding opportunities**.
- Carry out some **pilot projects** at a small scale to upscale it in future.

- Use **government and institutional support** like public funds and programmes.
- Create a **matchmaking programme**, focusing on early-stage funding and collaboration opportunities.

For Area 3 - Address skills gaps, the proposed solutions as follows:

- Balance resources irrespective of all challenges with respect to IPR protection, labour law, and insurance issues.
- Enabling the **sharing of non-bureaucratic resources** among personnel of collaborating organizations can help build capacities. For example, during a public funding phase, some organizations may face overcapacity and underfunding, while others have funding but lack experts. Having a mechanism in place to balance available resources (e.g., personnel) could significantly contribute to balancing budgets and providing opportunities for researchers and experts to build their careers and advance their topics. For instance, "hiring" experts on a project basis to address specific challenges.
- Organize joint **events for knowledge/experience sharing**.
- Organize **team-building events** and create opportunities where startups can meet/find business partners/team members.
- Create a team that will prepare a state-of-the-art analysis.
- Create a **cross-border entrepreneurial educational scheme** for researchers dealing with research in green technologies and cleantech to turn research results into marketable innovations.
- Launch **mentorship programmes**, bridge skill gaps, and align with market needs.

Area 4 - Inadequate public procurement regulations for innovations proposed solutions included:

- Provide **fast funding and support options** for inventors.
- Organize **events for policymakers** to learn from more developed countries how to improve the regulations.
- **Analyse the existing regulations**; prepare recommendations for the policy-level institutions.
- Put in place a **training programme** to help public organizations run innovative procurement schemes.
- There is a need for **events and expert panels** that would involve not only government officials but also representatives from venture capital and startups.
- Make a roundtable for ideas on **how to adjust the public procurement law to the specific needs** of innovators (with the representatives of various categories, including national lawmakers!)
- Advocate for and work with policymakers to establish pilot procurement programmes that prioritize cleantech solutions.

For Area 5 - Develop innovation hubs, the proposed solutions as follows:

- Develop a **basis for an interregional innovation hub** in the green/cleantech sector.
- Organize **joint events** to boost the interest of potential hub members to join and disseminate in their networks and ecosystems.
- Organise a **transnational hub** to allow for the exchange of personnel and best practices.
- Carry out **joint projects supported by regional funds**.
- Organise webinars or other types of regular practices for **the exchange of expert/organization contacts**.

- Build a strong community with networking events and mentorship programmes.
- Create a map of all regional institutions supporting startups - joint communication channel.
- Bring together experts from academia, industry, and government sectors to focus on cleantech development.

BREAKOUT ROOM 2

Moderator: Agnieszka Włodarczyk

Figure 5: ED Workshop PART II breakout room 2 solutions

For Area 1 - Promoting Cross-Regional Collaboration, the proposed solutions were as follows:

- Carry out cross-border pilot projects to test and upscale clean technologies.
- Carry out joint research, exchange, and training programmes.
- More academic: analyse/study successful examples of state and cleantech integration schemes and projects to define what is lacking in your country and try to apply them (legally, systematically, etc.).
- Establish cross-regional public-private partnerships to co-invest in large-scale cleantech projects.
- At this level, a lack of action-oriented initiatives to make collaborations a reality. Bringing concrete opportunities for collaboration is what worked best in the past.

For Area 2 - Support startups and spinoffs with financial instruments, proposed solutions included:

- Create a public-private venture fund for early-stage green/cleantech startups.
- Organize (educational/informative) sessions of providers and receivers of deep tech solutions.
- Provide support to startups for investment readiness and presenting them to investors.
- Promote innovative vouchers.

- Support cluster companies focused on cleantech and stimulate co-creation of financial instruments.
- Public funding can be designed as an enabler of access to private funding.
- Regional development agencies could involve private investors in the decision-making process to support projects with public funding.
- Create targeted acceleration programmes.

For Area 3 - Address skills gaps, the proposed solutions as follows:

- Create joint programmes with the participation of BSOs, academia, and SMEs for developing skills related to cleantech; consult them with leaders from the industry, academia, and government sectors. If it is not possible, everybody can prepare a report for their country.
- Create a good e-learning platform to encourage EC to promote the best solutions.
- Foster the participation of industry representatives in academic training programmes.
- Try to leverage micro-credential approaches to efficiently answer the training needs.
- Create cross-regional skills exchange programmes for professionals.

Area 4 - Inadequate public procurement regulations for innovations proposed solutions included:

- Foster establishment of 'regulatory sandboxes' as spaces for experimentation with existing and new regulations, engaging relevant stakeholders in the making of such regulations⁵.
- Provide training of public procurers on innovation procurement.
- Create state-owned "sandboxes" for early-stage cleantech startups in order to provide shorter time-to-market time for the successful ones.
- Organize open pitch days for administration to understand the innovative products and services timeline.
- Implement the living lab methodology and “test before investing”.
- Adjustment of legislation -more advanced green procurement- to guarantee acceptance of cleantech technologies.

For Area 5 - Develop innovation hubs, the proposed solutions as follows:

- Develop the basis for an interregional innovation hub in the green/cleantech sector.
- Promote space for meetings/encounters and dissemination of innovation in public and accessible places such as libraries.
- Get inspired from the Thematic Smart Specialization Platforms⁶.
- Organize more specific workshops and training instead of working on similar topics.
- Create a good e-learning platform to encourage EC to promote the best solutions.
- The EU Digital Innovation Hubs would be among the driving forces. Be careful to not reinvent the wheel but rather seek multi-disciplinary collaboration opportunities between existing hubs. Also, foster the emergence of communities of practice like in the regional thematic platforms.

⁵ <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC130458>

⁶ https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/policy/communities-and-networks/s3-community-of-practice/thematic_platforms_en#:~:text=Thematic%20Smart%20Specialisation%20Partnerships%20

BREAKOUT ROOM 3
Moderator: Julia Bauer

Figure 6: ED Workshop PART II breakout room 3 solutions

For Area 1 - Promoting Cross-Regional Collaboration, the proposed solutions were as follows:

- Create an interactive map for stakeholders (mostly corporations, but VCs, etc.) about innovations across Europe.
- Map regional strengths to create knowledge hubs and establish communication among them (e.g., Portugal Agriculture, Estonia digital).
- Organize regional events focused on networking and specific themes.
- Create acceleration consortia/programmes for specific neighbouring countries with partners from those countries (maybe not the whole EU as it is too widespread, and problems are too diverse).
- Organize cross-regional and industry events and projects with participants from the academia, industry, etc.
- Create regional hubs focused on specific areas and gather all regional stakeholders representing a given sector, managed by clusters or technology parks.
- Implement better regional policies concerning the diffusion of information on interregional collaboration opportunities.

For Area 2 - Support startups and spinoffs with financial instruments, proposed solutions included:

- Create public-private venture fund for early-stage green tech and digital startups.
- Temporary crisis related budgets for governments to co-invest (else free market).
- Create a co-investment fund that is focused on very early-stage companies together with business angels/accelerators to incentivize them to put more money into those startups.
- Training, or rather coordinated PR in VC and business angel organizations, about what is going on in the cleantech industry and why to invest in cleantech companies (best practices shared).

- Provide safe, low-risk funding schemes for pilot projects on the regional level.

For Area 3 - Address skills gaps, the proposed solutions as follows:

- A toolkit to support the creation of national hubs for innovation that cooperate with universities, VC & Angel associations, accelerators, and Cleantech for Europe.
- Online learning tools, platforms.
- Balancing resources: (irrespective of all challenges concerning IPR protection, labour law, and insurance issues).
- Enabling unbureaucratic resource sharing amongst personnel of collaborating organizations can help build capacities. I.e., under conditions of the public funding phase, organizations eventually have overcapacity and underfunding, while others have funding but lack experts. Having a mechanism in place to balance available resources (i.e., personnel) might significantly contribute to balancing budgets and provide opportunities for researchers and experts to build their careers and advance on their topics.
- Create corporate academies in innovative companies (co-founded by governments or the EU) for employees and young talents.
- Providing tools and financial resources for study visits and peer learning from other regions.

Area 4 - Inadequate public procurement regulations for innovations proposed solutions included:

- Certification/clean label supports European clean innovation label.
- Less requirements concerning long experience and financial investment.
- Technological sovereignty is becoming an increasingly important issue in procurement policies. What might be reasonable for critical infrastructure might become an obstacle to innovative companies, especially when these two areas intertwine. Having a comprehensible sovereignty test at hand could help organisations navigate this complex topic and make the right procurement decisions.
- Lower the requirements so that smaller innovation supporters like accelerators and incubators can take part.
- There must be a coherent policy framework across sectors and borders to ensure that Europe's cleantech industry can compete on a global scale with the input from Cleantech for Europe.

For Area 5 - Develop innovation hubs, the proposed solutions as follows:

- Develop the basis for an interregional innovation hub in the green/cleantech sector.
- In collaboration with universities - take advantage of the already existing framework.
- Ensure sustainability – set structure and funding.
- Create regional think-tanks.
- Acquire funding specifically for educating people on why innovation is important.

PHASE II of the Breakout rooms

PRESENTATION AND VOTING (10 Minutes)

This session, lasting 10 minutes, focused on individual work. Each participant presented their proposed solutions, after which they voted for the idea or solution, they considered the highest priority by placing green dots on post-it notes in the Miro board. The idea or solution receiving the most green dots was selected for further development during PHASE III of the breakout room interactive session.

In Breakout Room 1, the solution that received the highest score was related to Area 3:

- **Launch mentorship programmes, bridge skill gaps, and align with market needs.**

In Breakout Room 2, the top-scoring solution also pertained to Area 3:

- **Foster the participation of industry representatives in academic training programs by leveraging micro-credentials to efficiently address training needs.**

In Breakout Room 3, the highest-rated solution again addressed Area 3:

- **Provide tools and financial resources for study visits and peer learning from other regions.**

The unanimous selection of solutions related to **Area 3: Address Skills Gaps** indicates that participants view this as a critical and foundational issue for innovation ecosystems.

PHASE III of the Breakout rooms

PROJECT IDEA CARDS (45 Minutes)

This 45-minute session centered on teamwork, where each group was tasked with completing an **idea card** for their selected solution using the provided template. The groups were instructed to address three key questions aimed at formulating a project idea:

- 1) **Collaboration opportunities/stakeholders:** *Which regions, industries, or institutions should be involved in addressing these challenges? Which organizations/entities are the key target audience for your solution?*
- 2) **Resources and tools:** *What key resources, funding, or infrastructure is required to implement your solution (if possible, to be quantified)?*
- 3) **Expected impact:** *How will this project contribute to sustainable growth and innovation in the Cleantech sector? What will be created, changed, or enhanced?*

BREAKOUT ROOM 1 - Project Idea Card

The selected idea/solution for this breakout room is to **Launch mentorship programs, bridge skill gaps and align with market needs.**

Figure 7: Breakout room 1 project idea card

1) Collaboration opportunities and stakeholders: Which regions, industries, or institutions should be involved in addressing these challenges? Which organizations/entities are the key target audience for your solution?

- A mixed participation of more experienced regions and less prepared regions to allow the exchange of knowledge and practice
- NGOs that support innovators
- Regional business leaders
- Accelerators (which aggregate startup needs) and institutions
- Business environment institutions, local authorities, universities, experienced business mentors, business angels
- Local/municipal business development organizations
- Inventors, including researchers
- Institutions: Universities and Research Centres
- Existing accelerators, successful ecosystems, or on a national level (countries with the best digitalization experience, like Estonia)
- Academic incubators
- Industries to express demand for innovation demand and market needs
- Regions: Denmark, Sweden, Finland: these regions have strong cleantech ecosystems and a rich network of experienced professionals.
- Key Target Audience: Cleantech Startups and SMEs

- Industries: Renewable Energy (Solar, Wind, Hydrogen); Circular Economy; and Waste Management.
- 2) **Resources and tools:** *What key resources, funding, or infrastructure is required to implement your solution (if possible, to be quantified)?*
- University money and infrastructure
 - Regional funding from ERDF
 - Regional funding (maybe with an access fee)
 - European Erasmus+ Program or Interreg Program
 - Regional and national programs
 - EIC Accelerator funding
 - EU funding (national and regional programs) for Business Environment. Institutions, universities, training centres and qualified business mentors and coaches should be involved
 - City infrastructure
 - Test labs and showrooms
 - The knowledge that accelerators and startup incubators possess on how to attract mentors, the methodology of workshops and educational sessions, etc. This is already available
 - Study visits
 - Annual innovation summit and pitch events
 - Workshops, webinars, and training modules
 - Digital platform for online mentoring and learning
 - Expert forum where people can ask questions and look for advice
- 3) **Expected impact:** *How will this project contribute to sustainable growth and innovation in the Cleantech sector? What will be created, changed, or enhanced?*
- More awareness among the involved stakeholders on technology solutions' potential impact on their business or daily lives.
 - Enhanced skills to address the market demand and develop solutions better fitting the market needs.
 - Better alignment of technology offers and demand in the cleantech field.
 - SMEs better adjusted to market conditions (especially on the international market) - a bigger rate of "survival" on the market! a chance for Europe to "beat" Asia in terms of innovations.
 - KPIs - number of new partnerships - initiatives - a collaboration among hubs/centres for innovations - learning initiatives, etc.
 - More startups and SMEs ready for investment
 - The speed and success rate of cleantech innovation, the market readiness of startups, and the level of cross-regional collaboration
 - More researchers prepared for business activity

BREAKOUT ROOM 2 - Project Idea Card

The selected idea/solution for this breakout room is to **foster the participation of industry representatives of academic training programmes (leverage micro-credentials approaches).**

Figure 8: Breakout room 2 project idea card

1) Collaboration opportunities and stakeholders: Which regions, industries, or institutions should be involved in addressing these challenges? Which organizations/entities are the key target audience for your solution?

- Private universities (more flexibility) organize sessions and courses with industry (practically oriented curriculum, internships)
- Private companies entering the education curriculum (practical courses)
- Mentorship is offered among people from academia and industry
- Student organizations as a grassroots movement.
- Involvement of strong, moderate and emerging innovation European ecosystems universities and private schools. This will help to understand the different approaches in different ecosystems.
- PhD students - A Practical Approach to Test Beds
- In the case of universities, promoting and strengthening both large, high-risk and small industry-related projects as the subject of master's theses or PhD projects.
- Expansion of the form of financing internships of university employees in industry to facilitate and develop a framework for cooperation.
- Academic incubators for entrepreneurs
- Sectoral chamber of industry
- Technology Transfer Centres
- Academic incubators for entrepreneur

2) Resources and tools: What key resources, funding, or infrastructure is required to implement your solution (if possible, to be quantified)?

- Funding: Industry-sponsored scholarships for students
- Open laboratories
- Pitch days - researchers present the outline of the concept of a PhD thesis to a group of industry companies
- Companies declare their interest and support researchers/PhD students in the pitch days-researchers present the outline of the concept of a PhD thesis to a group of industry companies.
- Contracts with companies to provide patronage over the fields & smart specializations - short-term learning courses & studies.
- Relatively easy access to the infrastructure of showrooms and laboratories for test beds.
- Resources: industry expert participation in teaching and mentoring students (for instance: 10 experts for 2 hours over a 6-month long period).
- Lab equipment for hands-on training on cleantech studies.
- Inspiring example for a bottom-up initiative: association of companies⁷.
- Fields of action: training for employees, motivation of school kids.
- Diversification of the scope and financial framework of innovation vouchers.
- Simplified awarding procedures - innovation vouchers rewarding cooperation between business and academia.
- Introduction of forms of financing internships of university employees in industry.
- Creation of a compact cleantech knowledge database (a database of recommended technology suppliers, use cases, references database of companies, networking platform).
- Instruments supporting the use of laboratory infrastructure, robots, and university human resources to support innovation in cleantech.

3) Expected impact: *How will this project contribute to sustainable growth and innovation in the Cleantech sector? What will be created, changed, or enhanced?*

- Partnerships: Practical doctorates in close cooperation with companies that support research projects financially, provide technologies, or offer resources needed to conduct the research.
- Bridging the gap by encouraging academia & business to run joint tests; for example, the Environmental Aerodynamics Laboratory or Laboratory of Energy Saving Building by Krakow University of Technology.
- Structured and complete cleantech knowledge (a database of recommended technology suppliers, use cases, references database of companies, networking platform).
- Create conditions for commercialization of the results from research.
- It will help to create a highly skilled workforce that is already well-equipped to face the challenges in the industry.
- Both sectors learn from each other in a more holistic approach and stay updated.
- Partnerships: Practical doctorates in close cooperation with companies that support research projects financially, provide technologies, or offer resources needed to conduct research.
- By integrating industry insights into academic curricula, it will help students with relevant skills that will meet industry needs.

⁷ <https://netforfuture.at/>

BREAKOUT ROOM 3 - Project Idea Card

The selected idea/solution for this breakout room is to **providing tools and financial resources for study visits and peer learning from other regions.**

Figure 9: Breakout room 3 project idea card

- 1) Collaboration opportunities and stakeholders:** *Which regions, industries, or institutions should be involved in addressing these challenges? Which organizations/entities are the key target audience for your solution*

 - Regional development agencies
 - Universities
 - Competence Centres
 - Accelerators
 - Technology parks
 - Living labs and testing/demo spaces
 - Regional authorities
 - Cleantech ecosystem organizations/clusters
 - Thematically aligned co-working spaces
 - Startup platforms.
- 2) Resources and tools:** *What key resources, funding, or infrastructure is required to implement your solution (if possible, to be quantified)?*

 - Central cleantech organizations for all countries (use EU toolkits to show best practices).
 - Innovation budgets from governments (Ex. in Estonia, Startup Estonia has devoted budget).
 - Cluster exchange EU scheme, Erasmus+ mobility scheme, EU funding.
 - Engage private money for these trips (study visits) for companies that are interested in expanding to other countries.
 - Simplified rules for resource sharing (finances & personnel) between organizations.
 - Regional technology showrooms

- Living labs or demonstration centres.
 - A managed WhatsApp group for cleantech clusters (before creating a big platform) and regional ones related to the general group.
 - Create a mentorship programme with industry experts.
 - Implement a scholarship programme for participants from underrepresented regions.
 - Pitching training sessions.
- 3) Expected impact:** *How will this project contribute to sustainable growth and innovation in the Cleantech sector? What will be created, changed, or enhanced?*
- New expertise gained and facilitated an easier way to access to expertise and knowledge
 - A growing network of collaborating organizations
 - New project ideas
 - Understanding the regional strengths - all countries have their strengths and solutions.
 - New consortia
 - Opportunities to extend your reach in terms of business development.
 - Scaling up exploitation opportunities and broadening the market scope
 - Identifying technology providers
 - Filling technology gaps
 - Promote case studies of successful collaborations.
 - Actionable feedback for the industry
 - Success story sharing, but also failure stories sharing (lessons learnt)
 - Increased pitching skills
 - Best practice exchange scheme.

4.5 Conclusions

The **ED Workshop PART II** successfully built upon the outcomes of **PART I** by focusing on the development of actionable project ideas to address key challenges identified. Participants from diverse Quadruple Helix (QH) ecosystems, representing academia, industry, government, and civil society across seven European countries, collaborated intensively during the workshop. The structured methodology ensured effective engagement and allowed participants to explore innovative ideas while formulating solutions to foster sustainable growth and address critical gaps in their respective ecosystems. Key achievements include:

- **Refinement of key areas:** Out of the nine collaboration areas identified in PART I, five were selected for focused discussion, reflecting their strategic importance and the feasibility of achieving meaningful outcomes within the workshop's timeframe.
- **Consensus on Area 3 - addressing skills gaps:** All breakout groups unanimously prioritized Area 3: Address Skills Gaps, underscoring its foundational role in enhancing innovation ecosystems. The emphasis on mentorship programs, industry-academia collaboration, and tools for peer learning reflects a shared commitment to building capacity and aligning skills with market demands.
- **Diverse and actionable solutions:** Each breakout room proposed solutions tailored to their assigned area:
 - *Breakout Room 1: Focused on mentorship programs to bridge skill gaps and align with market needs.*
 - *Breakout Room 2: Advocated for integrating industry insights into academic training through micro-credentials.*
 - *Breakout Room 3: Highlighted the importance of study visits and peer learning to foster cross-regional knowledge exchange.*
- **Comprehensive project idea development:** Using a standardized template, participants developed detailed project idea cards that outlined collaboration opportunities, resource

requirements, and expected impacts. These ideas provide a clear pathway for advancing the EMPOWEREDbyNEIA initiative and beyond.

- **Enhanced collaboration across stakeholders:** The workshop fostered a co-creative environment, bringing together stakeholders from diverse sectors and regions. This collaboration not only strengthened cross-regional partnerships but also created opportunities for practical project implementation.

5. Result of feedback survey

After the conclusion of the workshops, a feedback survey was distributed to participants to gather their input on the outcomes of the event ([EU survey feedback form](#)).

In total, **15 respondents** completed the survey. The feedback was overwhelmingly positive, with 10 participants indicating they were very satisfied and 5 participants expressing satisfaction with the organization of the workshop. The results are also illustrated in the chart below.

Figure 10: Feedback of participants to the organisation of the ED Workshops

Moreover, all respondents expressed a strong interest in participating in future collaborations and projects, and many indicated their willingness to sign an expression of interest for future cross-regional cooperation.

6. Conclusions and next steps

The Entrepreneurial Discovery (ED) Workshops achieved the core objective of EMPOWEREDbyNEIA project by fostering cross-regional collaboration and addressing critical challenges within the Cleantech innovation ecosystems. Through a structured methodology and active engagement of Quadruple Helix (QH) stakeholders—representing academia, industry, government, and civil society—the workshops laid a strong foundation for impactful initiatives and sustainable development in the Cleantech sector.

Building on the results of the Entrepreneurial Discovery (ED) Workshops, the next key steps for the EMPOWEREDbyNEIA project are as follows:

- **Policy Recommendations and alignment:** Insights and findings from the workshops will contribute to the development of D2.2 Policy Brief, ensuring that the proposed project ideas and collaboration areas align with regional and EU-level policy frameworks.
- **Development of the Joint Action Plan:** The actionable project ideas and identified collaboration areas will serve as the foundation for creating the Joint Action Plan under WP3. This plan will outline concrete steps to foster cross-regional innovation and drive sustainable development in the Cleantech sector.
- **Sustained stakeholder engagement:** Mechanisms for continuous engagement with Quadruple Helix stakeholders will be established, leveraging the strong interest expressed by participants in future collaborations. This ongoing engagement will ensure a co-creative process and long-term collaboration among regions.

The ED Workshops have not only highlighted key challenges but have also provided a roadmap for actionable solutions. These outcomes reflect a collective commitment to advancing regional innovation ecosystems and achieving sustainable growth across Europe.

7. Annexes

Annex 1

ED Workshop PART I – Invitation email template

Subject: Invitation to participate in “Entrepreneurial Discovery Workshop” in the framework of the “EMPOWEREDbyNEIA” Horizon Europe project on the EU Regional Innovation Ecosystems

Dear **Mr. / Ms....**,

I hope this email finds you well.

Following up on our interview on **(DATE XXXX)**, we are writing to invite you to participate in an Entrepreneurial Discovery Workshop on Cleantech organised by the EMPOWEREDbyNEIA consortium. The Workshop aims to bring together representatives from academic, industry, government, and public sectors to jointly identify collaboration opportunities within the innovation ecosystems of seven EU countries (Austria, Bulgaria, Croatia, Estonia, Italy, Poland, and Romania). You can find below the agenda of the workshop:

Workshop Details:

Date: 10th of July 2024

Time: 10 AM - 12 AM (CEST)

Location: Zoom

Agenda

10:00 - 10:10: Welcome and Introduction

10:10 - 10:15: Overview of the EMPOWEREDbyNEIA project

10:15 - 10:20: Overview of Quadruple Helix Stakeholders & Entrepreneurial Discovery

10:20 - 10:40: Presentation of SWOT analysis on seven ecosystems

10:40 - 11:40: Roundtable discussion on strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats in each region

11:40 - 12:00: Discussion results and next steps

- Finding opportunities/ideas for cross-border collaboration and developing joint projects
- Collection of inputs/feedback for Workshop PART II

12:00: Wrap-up and closing

We believe that your insights and expertise will greatly contribute to the success of this workshop. Your participation will help identify areas for future actions as well as to foster cross-regional collaboration in general.

To sign up for the event, please [click here](#) to register.

Should you have any questions or require further information, feel free to reach out to me/us.

We look forward to your participation and contributions to this collaborative effort.

Sincerely,

[Your Name/Signature]

Annex 2

ED Workshop PART II – Invitation email template

Invitation Email Template

Subject: Follow-up Invitation to “Entrepreneurial Discovery Workshop-PART II”

Dear **Mr. / Ms.....,**

I hope this email finds you well.

Thank you again for your valuable participation in the first Entrepreneurial Discovery Workshop of the [EMPOWEREDbyNEIA](#) initiative. As a follow-up, we’re excited to invite you to PART II of the Workshop on October 22nd, 2024, from 10:00 to 12:30 CET. This session will continue building on the insights gathered during PART I and will focus on collaborative opportunities for joint projects across the Cleantech sector.

The agenda will be shared in the coming days. We believe your expertise will once again be a key contribution to the success of the workshop and future cross-regional actions.

Please [[click here to register](#)] for the event.

Should you have any questions or need further details, don’t hesitate to reach out.

We look forward to your continued participation and collaboration.

Sincerely,

[Your Name/Signature]